

Data Management Plan

General Information

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Project Title

Progression of Revenue and IMDb Score of Oscar “Best Picture” Winners From 1986 Until 2016

Project Acronym

OMRSP

Project Abstract

This experiment serves the purpose of investigating how the gross revenue (USA) and the IMDb user score of movies that were awarded an Oscar in the category *Best Picture* have evolved and fluctuated over the last three decades. More specifically, movies that were released between 1986 and 2016 are investigated.

It builds upon two data sources, one of which provide data about Oscar awarded movies. The other one is a compilation of general information about movies that are publicly accessible via the IMDb website.

When processing these datasets, the relevant information is assembled by *matching* movie entries from both sources. In the context of this experiment, two films are defined to be equal if and only if their titles and release years are equal.

Level of Distribution

This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. It is attributed to Raffael Foidl and published at Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4662139](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4662139)

Time Frame

From 2021-03-16 until 2021-04-19.

Keywords

movies, movie industry, imdb, data history, movie awards, oscars, academy award, best picture

Relevant Policies

- TU Wien Data Protection Policy
<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Documents/Data%20Protection%20Guidelines/Data%20Protection%20Policy.pdf>
- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management
<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>

History of Changes

Version	Publication Date	Changes
v1.3	2021-04-07	Fix typo in General Information Specify time frame explicitly
v1.2	2021-04-06	Add e-mail address of project creator Specify license, keywords and policies explicitly Add DOI badge for machine-actionable DMP
v1.1	2021-04-04	Add DOI badge for DMP Fix incorrect DOI badge images Add note regarding Zenodo metadata export
v1.0	2021-04-04	Initial version

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1 Data Description and Collection or Re-Use of Existing Data

1.1 Data Creation and Re-Use

The research data will be produced by utilization of a Python script specifically conceived for this purpose. This has the advantage that changes are quickly adopted without the need of a separate compilation step. Furthermore, it is a relatively lightweight, platform-independent technology, which inherently provides support for all popular operating systems and machines with reasonably modern hardware. The module dependencies of the Python script have been kept to a minimum for facilitated interoperability, namely `matplotlib` and `numpy`.

The data processing part of this project is based on two publicly available datasets:

1. Fontes, Raphael. (2020, February). The Oscar Award, 1927 - 2020, Version 7. Retrieved March 27, 2021 from <https://www.kaggle.com/unanimad/the-oscar-award/version/7>. 892 KB.
2. Grijalva, Daniel. (2017, October). Movie Industry, Version 2. Retrieved March 27, 2021 from <https://www.kaggle.com/danielgrijalvas/movies/version/2>. 953 KB.

The above-mentioned Python script reads local copies of these two datasets, compiles the information relevant for this experiment and produces the output data. The datasets will be distributed along with the script's source code. Their origin will be documented in the source repository.

1.2 Produced Data Files

The result of this project consists of two distinct artifacts.

1. The raw result data representing the compilation of the information gathered during the experiment. It is encoded in a simple CSV format with fields ("columns") for each attribute of output records. Since the experiment yields one output record per year and it targets a timespan of 31 years (from 1986 until 2016), this raw data file with about 30 lines will take up less than 100 KB of disk space.
2. Additionally, a visualization of the data described above is generated. For widespread compatibility, the image is rendered in the PNG format. Again, the storage requirement for this file is relatively low and, even with a decent resolution, will not exceed 500 KB.

Since the nature of the experiment's question is very specific, there are no community guidelines or standards as to how such data is preferably formatted. In theory, it is within the realms of possibility to generate an ontological representation of the output data instead of or in addition to the CSV file. The `dbpedia` ontology¹ or one specifically

¹<https://wiki.dbpedia.org/services-resources/ontology>

created for this use case would be candidates for this purpose.

Although the potential benefits of results that are linkable by URIs are acknowledged, it was decided against doing so. This decision is founded upon the simplicity and relatively low expected utility of the results to the majority of the community. Additionally, as the produced data are just a compilation of publicly available information, it is highly likely that the information is already available through the dbpedia knowledge graph, even if not as consolidated as with the CSV file.

2 Documentation and Data Quality

2.1 FAIR Data

The data and source code produced over the course of this experiment will adhere to the FAIR principles.

The artifacts will be findable because they are published to Zenodo, an open-access repository. They are equipped with a permanent and persistent identifier, a DOI². In addition to the Zenodo record, the data is also indexed and publicly findable in a GitHub repository³ that links to the Zenodo record via aforementioned DOI. Both repository entries provide metadata information that facilitate finding the experiment – for more information on metadata, see also subsection 2.2.

All (digital) information related to the project is available in data repositories that are accessible by means of searching the World Wide Web. They are open, i.e. there are no access restrictions – neither to the source datasets, the result datasets nor the experiment’s source code. Furthermore, the data repositories exhibit metadata about the published artifacts.

Interoperability is ensured by the employment of standardized and open formats such as CSV and PNG, i.e. no proprietary software is needed to read or modify the files produced. Furthermore, the documentation, which is also part of the contents indexed in the repositories, contains explanations as to the meaning of the data fields (“columns”) of the raw output data file. This knowledge, in combination with the well-known specification of the CSV format, allows for further processing in a (semi-)automatic way. It is also worth mentioning that Zenodo supports exporting the provided metadata in machine-actionable formats (e.g. DataCite, Dublin Core, DCAT)

The reusability of result data is ensured by the extensive documentation and additional metadata (see subsection 2.2) that accompany the data related to the experiment. This also entails information on the conditions that may apply for reusing data or code conceived for the purpose of this project.

²The URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4661145> always resolves to the most current version of the project, where the DOI of the latest release can be found.

³<https://github.com/raffaelfoidl/omrsp-code>

2.2 Organization, Metadata and Documentation

The data is organized in files and folders in the file system. The structure and naming convention is explained in the documentation that will be attached to the project files. Changes are tracked automatically through the use of `git`. The release of versions denoting specific project milestones are designated with the help of `git`'s concept of *tags*.

Although there are movie-specific metadata standards, they are not directly applicable to this experiment because it does not directly deal with information about movies in the narrower sense (e.g. duration, language, encoding, ...). At first, it was contemplated to use the controlled vocabulary provided by the *Dublin Core Metadata Initiative* (DCMI)⁴ because of its domain-agnosticism and simplicity. However, in the end, the *Ecological Metadata Language* (EML)⁵ was chosen for its greater expressiveness.

Even though EML specializes in earth and environmental sciences, it is well-suited and increasingly often used to describe metadata in other disciplines as well. Information such as creator, contact details, keywords, descriptions of the produced data files (e.g. the meaning of fields in the CSV file) will be serialized into an XML file and will form part of the documentation attached to the other project-related files. For facilitated creation of the metadata file, the tool `ezEML`⁶ will be used. Standard compliance of the produced XML file will be verified using the online version of the official *EML Validity Parser*⁷.

Metadata of the produced diagram will be provided in textual form. This includes – among other pieces of information – image resolution, pixels per meters, MIME type and file size. The creation of this metadata file can be achieved with various online tools, e.g. *Metadata2Go*⁸.

The source code will be documented in Python's *docstring* format. From these code comments, an HTML source code documentation will be generated that can be viewed in a browser.

A data flow diagram gives a high-level explanation of the data processing steps involved in the experiment.

Finally, a README file completes the documentation with an explanation of the file and folder structure, reused datasets and instructions for use cases such as running the code and re-generating the documentation.

2.3 Data Quality Control

Since, by nature of this project, the input and output data are static, there is no need for (re-)calibration or repeated measurements and data reviews. However, consistency

⁴<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

⁵<https://eml.ecoinformatics.org/>

⁶<https://ezeml.edirepository.org/>

⁷<https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/emlparser>

⁸<https://www.metadata2go.com/>

and correctness checks will be performed on a sample basis, as well as code refactorings to improve maintainability.

3 Storage and Backup During the Research Process

3.1 Data Storage and Backup

Changes to any files immediately relevant to the project during the development process are tracked as a result of employing the `git` version control system. The files themselves are primarily hosted on GitHub. Thus, the most recent state of the project files including differences to previous versions are always accessible via GitHub. Selected, important snapshots, so-called *releases*, are also published to and archived by Zenodo.

Additionally, there are two self-maintained backup strategies. Firstly, a manual backup is performed twice a week and stored on an external drive in the possession of the project creator. Secondly, the local development environment (representing the files that are also hosted on GitHub) is mirrored, i.e. automatically synchronized, with the personal Nextcloud instance of the project creator. This Nextcloud instance runs on a virtual private server (VPS) situated in Austria. The VPS provider also performs regular backups as a service for their customers.

It is acknowledged that keeping copies in the form of standalone hard drives is not an ideal backup strategy. However, considering the manageable size of the project, this approach – in combination with the other storage mediums mentioned above – achieves enough data redundancy to cover for potential data loss at one medium.

3.2 Data Security and Protection

As data is stored on multiple, completely independent, storage mediums (GitHub, Zenodo, HDD, VPS), the likelihood of an all-encompassing incident is extremely low. Thus, temporary or permanent loss of data on one or even multiple mediums is not a major complication because, in almost any case, there exists another copy of the data somewhere else. This holds true especially since GitHub and Zenodo for themselves already have measures in place that aim to prevent data loss.

Write-access to the data, i.e. modification rights, are exclusive to the project creator. This includes account credentials and privileges to GitHub, Zenodo, Nextcloud as well as physical access to the development machine and backup drive. All storage mediums that are accessed over a network are only addressed via TLS, i.e. over a secure communication channel which obstructs the interception of usernames and passwords.

The project neither processes nor produces sensitive or personal data. Hence, no privacy-related actions to protect any of the data need to be taken.

As the experiment is conducted in the context of Vienna University of Technology, the institutional data protection policy⁹ applies.

4 Legal and Ethical Requirements, Codes of Conduct

4.1 Personal Data

This project does not deal with personal data. As a consequence, there is no requirement for explicitly defined measures to comply with the legislation on personal data and security.

4.2 Intellectual Property

All project members will jointly own the artifacts produced – this encompasses source code as well as data – and have the right to control access. The software created as part of this project will be freely and openly available under the MIT license¹⁰. The experiment output data will be published under the Creative Commons CC0 license¹¹.

This has, among other things, two explicitly outlined consequences:

1. Project members retain the right to make modifications to the published data and/or source code at any point in time. In other words, there is an ever-present possibility of new versions of the produced dataset and visualization being published.
2. Simultaneously, anyone accessing the generated data is free to use, modify and distribute it – for private and commercial purposes.

The two datasets this experiment is based on (see subsection 1.1) are also both licensed under CC0.

4.3 Ethical Issues, Codes of Conduct

There are no ethical issues anticipated regarding data that is used or produced over the course of the experiment. Therefore, no special guidelines on how (long) to store and transfer data need to put in place. Similarly, there will not arise problem areas such as hiding data from or prohibiting the use of data for specific (groups of) people for ethical or legal reasons.

⁹<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Documents/Data%20Protection%20Guidelines/Data%20Protection%20Policy.pdf>

¹⁰<https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT>

¹¹<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/legalcode>

5 Data Sharing and Long-Term Preservation

5.1 Modalities of Data Sharing, Restrictions

All changes to the project – be it alterations in the input/output data or the source code – will be made public immediately in the GitHub repository mentioned in subsection 2.1. Specific milestones in the project are designated by *releases* which can be observed on GitHub, too. Additionally, for every release (i.e. substantial parts of the project have changed, not only metadata), a new DOI is generated and accessible on the general-purpose data repository Zenodo – see also the linked target DOI URL in subsection 2.1.

There is no embargo period nor any other restriction on the re-use of data: All data related to this project will be made available to everyone immediately.

5.2 Data Preservation

Due to the small file sizes of the datasets consumed and produced, every piece of input and output data, the documentation and the source code will be archived. The attached documentation contains a detailed list the specific files that are contained in this enumeration. This enables reproducing the results in any case, but also provides the actual results of the specific project version right away. No “runtime” such as a Python virtual environment will be archived since it is not strictly related to the experiment data. For this reason, there are instructions for creating such an environment in the documentation.

GitHub does not explicitly state the preservation time of their code repositories, but claims that it “(...) *intends to keep your public repositories available unless you remove them*”¹². Zenodo is more specific and promises a retention period of its own lifetime, which amounts to at least the next 20 years¹³. In both cases, this is in accordance with the TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management¹⁴

The target audience of the data produced might be researchers with a focus on recent developments in the movie industry. It is also possible that the results are relevant for people interested in the history and development of movie popularity and Oscar awards.

5.3 Software Required for Using and Reproducing the Results

In order to use the results of the experiment, no special software is needed. The data can be accessed from one of the repositories – GitHub, Zenodo – with an ordinary web browser over the internet. The data themselves can be used on every major platforms without any special or proprietary software. The chosen formats CSV for the raw data

¹²<https://docs.github.com/en/github/creating-cloning-and-archiving-repositories/about-archiving-content-and-data-on-github>

¹³<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

¹⁴<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>

and PNG for the chart are universally supported with software that is almost always part of the operating system.

As for the reproduction of the observed results, there are mainly two options. The first one was already hinted at in subsection 5.2 above. Since the experiment is implemented as a Python script, it can be executed using a local Python interpreter – detailed instructions are given in the documentation. If, however, no installation of Python is available nor desired, there is also a Dockerfile provided. With the help of this file, the experiment can be run in an isolated Docker container such that no project dependencies have to be installed directly on the local machine.

5.4 Persistent Identifiers

A DOI is assigned to the source code using the Zenodo and GitHub integration (see subsection 2.1). Additionally, a DOI is assigned to the data produced in the experiment.

Table 1 provides a summary of the persistent identifiers that have been reserved for the project and the location of the source code repository on GitHub. The DOI badges always resolve to the latest version available.

Data Object	DOI or Location
Source Code Repository	https://github.com/raffaelfoidl/omrsp-code
Source Code (Including Produced Data)	DOI
Produced Data (Standalone)	DOI
Data Management Plan	DOI
Machine-Actionable Data Management Plan	DOI

Table 1: DOIs and Locations of Project Components

6 Data Management Responsibilities and Resources

6.1 Responsibilities

Raffael Foidl is responsible for implementing the DMP and all other data management tasks that are related to the project. This includes, for instance, ensuring the DMP is

reviewed and revised regularly. Furthermore, metadata production, backup generation and keeping the documentation up to date are also in his area of responsibility.

6.2 Resources

There is no need in this project for special hardware or software that is not available for free. Nor is external or specifically trained staff required for FAIR data management that would need to be accounted for in a budget.

Furthermore, the data repositories employed do not apply any charges for this project.